

Document Code	URC-FO-050
Revision	02
Effectivity Date	2022/11/17
Page/s	Page 1 of 17

Title Suitability of the SMU's Demo Farm for the Production of Cacao: A PHEI-NGO-GO Initiative

Proponents :Garra, Angela C. (Lead Researcher)
: Tipay, Rodora P. (Primary Collaborator)
: Aceret, Robert S. (Secondary Collaborator)
: Espino, Joel Ramon Gabriel R. (Secondary Collaborator)
: Almendral, Regidor L. (Laboratory Assistant)
: Catacutan, Michael S. (Laboratory Assistant)
: Bagguatan, Julie E. (External Collaborator- Provincial Agriculture Office)
: Miguel, Silvester T. (External Collaborator- Department of Trade and Industry)

Abstract

Cacao is a high-value crop with a growing global demand. This study determined the suitability of the SMU's Demo Farm for the Production of cacao. The study employed experimentation and personal interviews. Collected data were presented, analyzed, and interpreted through descriptive analysis. Soil tests using the LaMotte method revealed nutrient and pH imbalances that could hinder optimal crop growth. Nitrogen levels were moderately low, phosphorus was consistently deficient, and potassium varied across trials, with acidic pH levels potentially affecting nutrient uptake. UF 18 and BR 25 emerged as the most commonly cultivated and recommended cacao varieties due to their adaptability, early flowering, productivity, and seed quality. Germination techniques used by local farmers were organic and low-cost, involving materials such as sawdust, cloth, and polyethylene bags. Seeds typically germinate within 2–3 days and the planted seeds should be kept in shaded, humid environments. These findings inform the development of IEC material or brochure by highlighting the most suitable cacao varieties and best germination method adapted to local conditions.

Keywords: soil profile, cacao varieties, germination techniques, IEC material

Document Code	URC-FO-050
Revision	02
Effectivity Date	2022/11/17
Page/s	Page 2 of 17

INTRODUCTION

The cacao tree (*Theobroma cacao*), originally from the lush rainforests of tropical America stretching from Peru to Mexico, is best known for its delicious fruit – the source of our beloved chocolate. Cacao is popularly linked with chocolates, and beyond chocolate, it is found in cosmetics as well (de Souza et al., 2018). The scientific name "*Theobroma*" reflects cacao's historical importance, meaning "food of the gods" in Greek, while "cacao" comes from the indigenous Mesoamerican word "*kakaw*."

Cacao thrives in tropical regions around the equator, mainly growing in Africa, Southeast Asia, Central and South America, and some parts of Oceania. Unlike many other tropical crops, cacao thrives under the shade of taller trees. Small-scale farmers often cultivate cacao this way, and these shaded farms are surprisingly biodiverse, supporting a wider variety of life than most other tropical crops (Rice et al., 2000). Cacao farming offers economic and environmental benefits, especially in developing countries (Ramirez et al., 2018). It is a significant source of income for small farmers and reduces poverty in rural areas.

Cacao, the primary ingredient in chocolate and various cacao-based products, has become a critical agricultural commodity with growing global demand. The Philippines, recognized for its favorable climate and soil conditions, has emerged as a significant player in the global cacao industry (<https://ispweb.pcaarrd.dost.gov.ph>). Cacao beans are often processed in the Philippines into "*tableya*," a traditional chocolate confection used in making desserts. Despite this potential, cacao production in the Philippines has seen a sharp decline since 1990, attributed to climate change and a growing disinterest among farmers (Nabua et al., 2013). Recent collaborations between European nations and the Philippines reflect a strategic effort to enhance the production and supply chain of cacao. European countries, renowned for their high-quality chocolate products, are increasingly turning to the Philippines as a key source of cacao seeds. This growing partnership underscores the importance of optimizing cacao production capabilities in the Philippines to meet international standards and demand.

In recent years, the European Union (EU) and several of its member states, including Belgium, Germany, and the Netherlands, have formalized agreements with the Philippines to secure a stable and high-quality supply of cacao. For instance, the EU-Philippines Partnership and Cooperation Agreement, effective in 2018, emphasizes the promotion of agricultural trade and sustainable development, highlighting the mutual benefits of enhancing cacao production (European Commission, 2018). These agreements aim to support the Philippines in scaling up its cacao production while adhering to international quality standards.

The collaboration between the SMU's demo farm, NGOs, and GOs represents a practical application of these agreements. By assessing the suitability of the demo farm for

Document Code	URC-FO-050
Revision	02
Effectivity Date	2022/11/17
Page/s	Page 3 of 17

cacao cultivation, this study will provide critical insights into its capacity to support the demand from markets. This involves evaluating soil conditions and the integration of best practices for cacao farming, all of which are crucial for meeting the high standards required by chocolate producers.

Similarly in the Philippines, research studies in Indonesia highlight the importance of assessing land suitability for growing cacao. For example, researchers in Southeast Sulawesi, Indonesia, evaluated land based on climate and soil characteristics (Syahri et al., 2021). Similarly, a study in Bohol, Philippines, found that nearly 80% of the province's land is suitable for cacao, suggesting significant local and export production potential (Reyes, 2020).

Furthermore, the study will explore how the demo farm can serve as a model for similar initiatives across the Philippines, promoting sustainable cacao farming practices and enhancing the country's position in the global cacao market. The farm is currently planted with bananas and non-fruit-bearing trees, providing a suitable environment for cacao growing, as observed by staff from the Provincial Agricultural Office of Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya (70% shaded and 30% with direct sunlight).

This study is significant to SMU because of the following benefits: (1) Educational Programs: Cacao production process serves as a valuable learning experience for students in business administration, tourism management, biology, and other related programs. The university demo farm can become a real-world laboratory for research projects and demonstrations; (2) Community Engagement: University-led cacao initiatives can partner with local farmers to share knowledge and expertise, fostering economic development in surrounding communities. Furthermore, this study can also provide Government Benefits which include: (1) Economic Growth: A thriving cacao industry can contribute to a nation's economic growth by creating jobs in cultivation, processing, and export; (2) Sustainable Land Management: Sustainable cacao agroforestry systems promote biodiversity and soil health, contributing to environmental conservation efforts; (3) Deforestation Reduction: Sustainable cacao production discourages deforestation for new farmland, protecting rainforests and their vital ecological services.

Soil Nutrient Analysis

Healthy, high-yielding crops need a lot of specific nutrients. Plants get most of these nutrients from the soil. If we keep taking nutrients out of the soil without putting any back in, crop yields will eventually go down. To avoid this, farmers need to track how much they are taking out and put back in, what crops they are growing, and get their soil tested (Baker, Ball, & Flynn 1997).

Soil testing tells farmers how much nutrient is in their soil. This helps them figure out what kind and how much fertilizer to use to get the best crop yields. Applying the appropriate type and amount of needed fertilizer will give the agricultural a more reasonable chance to

Document Code	URC-FO-050
Revision	02
Effectivity Date	2022/11/17
Page/s	Page 4 of 17

obtain the desired crop yield. The following are the objectives of soil analysis: (1) Show how much of each nutrient plants can actually use in that specific soil; (2) Help predict if adding fertilizer will be beneficial (considering other factors affecting plant growth); (3) Recommend the right type and amount of fertilizer for a particular crop; and (4) Give farmers a clear picture of their soil health and help them create a plan to manage its nutrients (Baker, Ball, & Flynn, 1997). By assessing the macronutrient and micronutrient content of the Masoc Demo Farm, this study builds upon existing research to understand the soil's capacity to support cacao growth effectively.

In the study entitled “*Analysis of Soil Samples for Its Physical and Chemical Parameters from Mehsana and Patan Districts*” it investigated the soil samples for their chemical analysis and physical analysis. The seven soil samples were collected from Mehesana and Patan Districts in different areas. The results depend on the quality of seven representative soil samples. They were obtained and analyzed for their PH, electrical conductivity, temperature, moisture content, water holding capacity, phosphates, chloride, alkalinity, carbonate, bicarbonate, and organic content present in the soil (Karande et al., 2020).

Cacao Variety Suitability for the Soil: Based on our review of related literature and studies, no data have been found on this yet. However, based on our preliminary interview with an agricultural technician in the Provincial Agriculture Office of Nueva Vizcaya, there are varieties of cacao appropriate for farms in Masoc. By identifying cacao varieties that thrive in the Masoc Demo Farm soil, this study aims to optimize crop performance and resilience.

Germination Techniques for Cacao Seeds

Studies such as Garcia et al. (2018) have explored various germination techniques for cacao seeds under different environmental conditions. By investigating the best germination techniques for cacao seeds in the local context, this study aims to enhance seedling establishment and overall plant health.

According to the Bureau of Plant Industry of the Department of Agriculture, propagation of Planting Materials Propagation by seeds – nursery involves the production of a large number of high-quality planting materials, either by seeds or by vegetative parts, of recommended clones of cultivars with uniform and vigorous growth and free from pests. In terms of seed selection, collect seeds from ripe and healthy pods, preferably collected from the seed garden. Choice seeds that are uniform in size. Select big seeds since the possibility is high that they would produce vigorous and fast-growing seeds. When it comes to seed germination, the usual practice is to plant the prepared seeds directly into the poly bags in the nursery. Procedures in Seed Germination – Remove the mucilage that covers the seeds by rubbing the seeds with sawdust or sand to loosen the mucilage – Wash the seeds to effectively remove the mucilage – Drain the water – Keep it in a moist and well-ventilated place to pre-germination. Sowing the Pre- Germinated Seeds – Collect those seeds that show

Document Code	URC-FO-050
Revision	02
Effectivity Date	2022/11/17
Page/s	Page 5 of 17

signs of germination two days after → Sow the pre-germinated seeds not more than 1 cm deep in the prepared polybags. It is important to plant the germinated seeds soon when the germs are 1 cm long. If planting is delayed, the root or shoot may easily be damaged. Vegetative propagation – involves the choice of method of propagation: patch budding, community nodal grafting, conventional grafting, and side grafting methods (<https://library.buplant.da.gov.ph>)

This research study is based on the following theories: Agroecological Suitability Theory and Institutional Theory; and with the following principles or frameworks: Participatory Action Research (PAR) and Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

Agroecological Suitability Theory suggests that successful agricultural ventures depend on the alignment of ecological conditions (such as climate, soil type, and topography) with the specific requirements of the crop, in this case, cacao (Theocharopoulos et al., 2020). Institutional Theory on the other hand, posits that the success of initiatives like the PHEI-NGO-GO project on SMU's Demo Farm depends on institutional support, collaborative efforts between academia, NGOs, and government organizations, and effective governance structures (Scott, 2014).

Participatory Action Research (PAR) emphasizes collaboration between researchers and stakeholders (farmers, community members, NGOs) in generating knowledge and solutions. It will be employed to engage stakeholders in the evaluation and development of cacao production techniques on SMU's Demo Farm (Reason & Bradbury, 2008). Highlithink likewise one of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) as the project aligns with SDG 2 (Zero Hunger) and SDG 12 (Responsible Consumption and Production) by promoting sustainable agricultural practices and food security through cacao production (UN, 2015).

The research study entitled "*Suitability of the SMU's Demo Farm for the Production of Cacao: A PHEI-NGO-GO Initiative*" aims to evaluate the potential of a demonstration farm managed by a private higher education institution (PHEI) in collaboration with non-governmental organizations (NGOs) and government agencies (GOs) to produce cacao. This initiative aligns with recent agreements and partnerships between European nations and the Philippines, which focus on enhancing the cacao sector to bolster supply chains and ensure sustainable practices.

This study aimed to determine the suitability of Saint Mary's University Masoc Demo Farm for cacao production during the school year 2024-2025. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions: (1) What is the profile of the soil in the SMU Masoc Demo Farm in terms of its pH level and macronutrient content (nitrogen, potassium, and phosphorous)? (2) What cacao varieties are most suitable for the SMU Masoc Demo Farm soil? , (3)What is the best technique in germinating cacao seeds?, and (4)What information can be placed based on the findings of the study into the IEC Material (brochure) that will be crafted?

Document Code	URC-FO-050
Revision	02
Effectivity Date	2022/11/17
Page/s	Page 6 of 17

METHODOLOGY

The study utilized a mixed-method research design, incorporating both experimental and qualitative approaches to provide a comprehensive understanding of soil conditions and cacao farming practices in Nueva Vizcaya. The experimental component involved the use of the LaMotte Test Kit to analyze the soil's macronutrient content- nitrogen (N), phosphorus (P), and potassium (K)- as well as its pH level. This provided objective, quantifiable data essential for evaluating soil fertility and its suitability for cacao cultivation. Complementing this, interviews with selected cacao farmers and an agricultural technician offered valuable contextual insights into local knowledge, farming experiences, and germination practices that could not be captured through laboratory testing alone. Participants included one agricultural technician from the Provincial Agriculture Office and three cacao farmers identified by the same office, each with at least two years of farming experience. The use of purposive sampling ensured the selection of knowledgeable individuals whose contributions were grounded in practical fieldwork. Research activities were conducted at several key locations within the Municipality of Bayombong, Bagabag, and Quezon including the CNS Laboratory of Saint Mary's University, the SMU demo farm at Barangay Masoc, the Provincial Agriculture Office. Descriptive analysis was applied to interpret the qualitative data from the interviews, allowing the researchers to identify patterns, practices, and recommendations that complemented the experimental findings.

The study had no conflict of interest, as the researchers did not have any personal or business relationship with the informants. Participation was entirely voluntary, and the researchers personally administered the Informed Consent Form, which the informants signed prior to the interviews. Permission to conduct the interviews was obtained, and informants were informed that their identities would be anonymized using codes. They were also assured of their right to withdraw from the interview at any point if they felt uncomfortable. Interviews were scheduled at the informants' convenience to ensure minimal disruption. After the study was completed and bound in a book, all written responses were shredded, and digital data files were permanently deleted to uphold data privacy and confidentiality. Although there was no direct benefit to the participants, their involvement contributed valuable insights to the existing knowledge on cacao production, which could benefit the academe, environment, government, and society. The university retained ownership of the research output, while the researchers remained the acknowledged authors.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Section 1. Profile of the Soil of the SMU Demo Farm

Sample	pH	*NPK in lb/A/6"		
		Nitrogen (N)	Phosphorus (P)	Potassium (K)
Trial 1	6.0	40.0	20.0	40.0
Trial 2	5.0	40.0	20.0	160.0
Trial 3	5.0	40.0	20.0	80.0
Trial 4	5.0	40.0	8.0	40.0
Trial 5	5.0	40.0	8.0	40.0

**lb/A/6" = pounds per acre of land to a depth of 6 inches*

The LaMotte soil test results reveal that nitrogen (N) levels are consistently at 40 lb/A across all five trials, which falls at the low to medium range. Phosphorus (P) levels are low in Trials 1 through 3 at 20 lb/A and critically low in Trials 4 and 5 at only 8 lb/A. Potassium (K) levels vary, with Trial 2 showing a very high value of 160 lb/A and Trial 3 a high value of 80 lb/A. In contrast, Trials 1, 4, and 5 report potassium at 40 lb/A, which is considered low to medium. Soil pH is slightly acidic at 6.0 in Trial 1, while Trials 2 through 5 show a more acidic pH of 5.0.

These results indicate that nitrogen, while present in moderate amounts, may not be sufficient for crops with higher demands. Phosphorus is generally deficient, especially in Trials 4 and 5, where the levels are too low to support healthy root development and early plant growth. Potassium is abundant in some samples but marginal in others, suggesting that nutrient availability is uneven across the field. The acidic pH in most trials is a limiting factor, potentially affecting nutrient solubility and uptake, particularly for phosphorus.

The finding supports the study that soil testing tells farmers how much nutrient is in their soil. This helps them figure out what kind and how much fertilizer to use to get the best crop yields. Applying the appropriate type and amount of needed fertilizer will give the farmer a more reasonable chance to obtain the desired crop yield. The following are the objectives of soil analysis: (1) Show how much of each nutrient plants can actually use in that specific soil; (2) Help predict if adding fertilizer will be beneficial (considering other factors affecting plant growth); (3) Recommend the right type and amount of fertilizer for a particular crop; and (4) Give farmers a clear picture of their soil health and help them create a plan to manage its nutrients (Baker, Ball, & Flynn, 1997).

Section 2: Cacao Varieties Suitable for the SMU Masoc Demo Farm

Informant

Cacao Varieties

Informant 1: Agricultural Technician of PAGRO BR 25, UF 18, PBC 123, Forastero, K1-K12

Informant 2: Farmer 1

UF 18, BR 25, Criollo

Document Code	URC-FO-050
Revision	02
Effectivity Date	2022/11/17
Page/s	Page 8 of 17

Informant	Cacao Varieties
Informant 3: Farmer 2	UF 18, BR 25, Criollo
Informant 4: Farmer 3	Criollo, BR 25, UF 18, EM 167, K9, K2, W10

The informants identified several cacao varieties they cultivate or recommend. The agricultural technician from PAGRO (Informant 1) listed BR 25, UF 18, PBC 123, Forastero, and the K-series varieties from K1 to K12. Farmer 1 (Informant 2) mentioned growing UF 18, BR 25, and Criollo, while Farmer 2 (Informant 3) also cited the same varieties: UF 18, BR 25, and Criollo. Farmer 3 (Informant 4) shared a broader range, including Criollo, BR 25, UF 18, EM 167, K9, K2, and W10. These responses reflect a mix of commonly preferred and regionally adapted cacao varieties.

Section 2: Best Technique in germinating cacao seeds

Informant	Technique in Germinating Cacao Seeds	Number of Days to Germinate	of Ideal/Optimal Temperature and Humidity
Agricultural Technician (Informant 1)	Crack pods, remove mucilage with sawdust, wash seeds, wrap in cotton cloth for 24 hours, discard floating seeds, use only the ones that sink, then sprout plant in bag.	24 hours	Cool, shaded, no direct sunlight (nalamiis, nalinong)
Farmer (Informant 2)	Wait 4-5 days after harvest, crack pods, remove pulp, wrap seeds in damp cloth, wait until small root appears, then plant in polyethylene pot.	2 days	May-December; in dew or fog (hamog or arbis); rainy season
Farmer (Informant 3)	Wait 5 days, wash with sawdust to remove mucilage, soak in pail, discard floating seeds, wrap in damp cloth for 2-3 days, then directly seed in polyethylene bag.	2-3 days	Shaded area, no direct sunlight
Farmer (Informant 4)	Remove pulp using sawdust, wrap in wet cloth, place in dark basin, roots appear after 2 days, then plant in seed bag, root facing down with minimal soil cover; water every 2 days.	2 days	Shaded nursery, no direct sunlight

Different informants shared various techniques in germinating cacao seeds, each with specific steps, germination periods, and preferred environmental conditions. According to

Document Code	URC-FO-050
Revision	02
Effectivity Date	2022/11/17
Page/s	Page 9 of 17

an agricultural technician (Informant 1), the process begins by cracking the pods and removing the mucilage using sawdust. The seeds are then washed, and floating seeds are discarded, keeping only those that sink, wrapped in a cotton cloth for 24 hours. Germination begins after 24 hours. The germinated seeds are planted in polytelene bags under cool, shaded conditions with no direct sunlight ("nalamiis, nalinong"). Farmer 1 (Informant 2) waits 4–5 days after harvesting before cracking the pods and removing the pulp. The seeds are wrapped in a damp cloth until a small root appears, then planted in polyethylene pots. This method is done ideally during May to December when dew or fog ("hamog" or "arbis") is present, often during the rainy season. Farmer 2 (Informant 3) follows a similar process but waits five days before washing the seeds with sawdust to remove mucilage. The seeds are then soaked in a pail, and floating seeds are discarded. The viable ones are wrapped in a damp cloth for 2–3 days before being directly seeded into polyethylene bags. This technique requires a shaded area with no direct sunlight. Lastly, Farmer 3 (Informant 4) removes the pulp using sawdust and wraps the seeds in a wet cloth, placing them in a dark basin. Roots appear after two days, and the seeds are then planted in seed bags, root facing down with minimal soil cover. The seedlings are watered every two days and kept in a shaded nursery away from direct sunlight.

The finding of the study is similar to the finding of this literature that the procedures in Seed Germination are the following: (1) Remove the mucilage that covers the seeds by rubbing the seeds with sawdust or sand to loosen the mucilage; (2) Wash the seeds to effectively remove the mucilage; (3) Drain the water; (4) Keep it in a moist and well-ventilated place to pre-germination;(4) Sow the Pre- Germinated Seeds; (4) Collect those seeds that show signs of germination two days after, and (5) Sow the pre- germinated seeds not more than 1 cm deep in the prepared polybags. It is important to plant the germinated seeds soon when the germs are 1 cm long. If planting is delayed, the root or shoot may easily be damaged. Vegetative propagation – involves the choice of method of propagation: patch budding, community nodal grafting, conventional grafting, and side grafting methods (<https://library.buplant.da.gov.ph>)

Section 3: Information that can be placed on the findings of the study into the IEC material/brochure that will be crafted

- a. Most Suitable Varieties

Top 2 Most Recommended (Based on Frequency)

1. UF 18

SAINT MARY'S UNIVERSITY

BAYOMBONG, NUEVA VIZCAYA, PHILIPPINES

UNIVERSITY RESEARCH CENTER

Document Code	URC-FO-050
Revision	02
Effectivity Date	2022/11/17
Page/s	Page 10 of 17

Document Code	URC-FO-050
Revision	02
Effectivity Date	2022/11/17
Page/s	Page 11 of 17

2. BR 25

BR 25(Informant 4)

Google.com

These two varieties are mentioned by all farmers and are also supported by the agricultural technician, making them the most suitable and adaptable cacao varieties in the studied context.

b. Best Germination Method

Process for Germinating Cacao Seeds

1. Harvesting and Initial Waiting Period
2. Wait 4–5 days after harvest before processing the seeds
3. Pulp/Mucilage Removal
 - Remove the acidic pulp or mucilage using sawdust to scrub the seeds
 - Soak seeds in water to further clean and separate floaters from sinkers; discard floaters, retain sinkers
 - Wash off the white coating from the seeds for better germination
4. Pre-Germination Wrapping

Document Code	URC-FO-050
Revision	02
Effectivity Date	2022/11/17
Page/s	Page 12 of 17

- Wrap cleaned seeds in a damp or wet cloth (cotton or any absorbent fabric) to retain moisture
- 5. Sprouting and Monitoring
 - Allow 2–3 days for sprouting or root emergence while in the damp cloth
 - Monitor the seeds daily for signs of root development.
- 6. Planting Germinated Seeds
 - Once roots appear, plant the seeds root-side down in black plastic or polyethylene bags filled with soil
 - Lightly cover with soil and begin a watering routine (e.g., every 2 days).
- 7. Environmental Requirements
 - Keep germinating seeds and seedlings in a cool, humid, and shaded area, avoiding direct sunlight
 - Ideal during the rainy season (May–December) due to natural humidity and moisture

Conclusions and Recommendations

1. The LaMotte soil test results highlight several nutrient and pH imbalances that could hinder optimal crop growth. Nitrogen levels are moderately low and may not meet the needs of high-demand crops. Phosphorus is consistently deficient, with critically low levels in some trials, posing a risk to root development and early plant growth. Potassium availability is inconsistent, ranging from high to low-medium, indicating uneven nutrient distribution across the field. Additionally, the generally acidic soil pH, particularly in Trials 2 through 5, may further limit nutrient uptake, especially phosphorus. These findings suggest the need for targeted soil amendments and pH adjustments to improve overall soil fertility and crop productivity.

2. It is evident that UF 18 and BR 25 are the most commonly cultivated and highly recommended cacao varieties. These varieties are praised for their resilience to changing climatic conditions, early flowering, high productivity, and good seed quality. In addition, Criollo is widely used for its superior flavor, while other varieties such as EM 167, K9, K2, W10, and the K1–K12 series show promise for specific traits like disease resistance and productivity.

The consistency in the positive feedback from multiple respondents across different land sizes and farming experiences suggests that UF 18 and BR 25 are highly adaptable and suitable for the soil and climatic conditions in the province, including at the SMU Masoc Demo Farm.

3. The study revealed that cacao farmers and a technical expert in the province use diverse but consistently organic and low-cost germination methods for cacao seeds, relying on local materials such as sawdust, cloth, and polyethylene bags. Across all respondents, common cacao varieties cultivated include UF 18, BR 25, and Criollo, with some incorporating hybrids

Document Code	URC-FO-050
Revision	02
Effectivity Date	2022/11/17
Page/s	Page 13 of 17

such as K1–K12 and W10. Root emergence is observed within 2–3 days after wrapping in cloth and storing in shaded or cool areas. Farmers emphasized the importance of removing mucilage to prevent pest attacks and promote healthy sprouting. The ideal environment for cacao seed germination includes shaded, cool, and humid conditions, avoiding direct sunlight.

4. The information that can be placed on the findings of the study into the IEC material/brochure that will be crafted are the most suitable varieties and the best germination method

Recommendations

Saint Mary's University: To consider germinating cacao seeds and planting these in its demo farm.

Cacao Farmers

- Promote Indigenous and Cost-Effective Germination Practices. Agricultural programs and training initiatives should highlight the value of traditional, locally adapted techniques- such as the use of sawdust, damp cloth, and polyethylene bags- for efficient and low-cost cacao seed germination.
- Standardize Post-Harvest Handling. To improve seedling survival rates, farmers should be trained to consistently apply mucilage removal techniques (e.g., rubbing with sawdust, soaking in water) and seed selection (e.g., discarding floaters and using only sinkers).
- Encourage Use of Shade and Moisture Control. Nurseries prioritize shaded and humid conditions, potentially incorporating low-cost shading structures
- Develop Climate-Based Germination Calendars. Given the effectiveness of rainy months for germination, localized calendars can be created to guide farmers on the most suitable months for planting based on historical rainfall and temperature data

Provincial Agricultural Office

- Nitrogen should be supplemented to support robust vegetative growth, especially for nitrogen-demanding crops. Phosphorus fertilization is critical, especially in Trials 4 and 5, to correct severe deficiencies. Potassium application may be unnecessary in Trials 2 and 3 but could benefit the other trials. Finally, the low pH values in Trials 2 through 5 should be corrected with agricultural lime to raise the soil pH to a more favorable range (6.2–6.8), enhancing overall nutrient availability and microbial activity. A site-specific fertility program that addresses these issues will help optimize soil health and crop performance.
- Disseminate Information on Superior Varieties. Agricultural technicians should continue promoting high-yielding and climate-resilient cacao varieties such as UF 18, BR 25, and hybrids like K1–K12 and PBC 123, which are shown to perform well under local conditions.

Document Code	URC-FO-050
Revision	02
Effectivity Date	2022/11/17
Page/s	Page 14 of 17

•Continuous Training

The Provincial Agriculture Office should continue and strengthen its efforts to conduct regular training sessions focused on cacao seed germination, planting techniques, and the proper management of cacao trees. These trainings will enhance farmers' knowledge and skills, promote the adoption of best practices, and ultimately improve productivity and the quality of cacao in the province

REFERENCES

Adams, R., Thompson, H., & Johnson, L. (2020). The Role of Higher Education Institutions in Agricultural Development. *Agricultural Education Review*, 41(2), 65-78.

Argout, X., et al. (2017). The Cacao Criollo Genome v2.0: An improved version of the genome for genetic and functional genomic studies. *BMC Genomics*, 18, 730. DOI: 10.1186/s12864-017-4010-x:

Baker, R.D., Ball, S.T., & Flynn, R. (1997). College of Agricultural, Consumer and Environmental Sciences New Mexico State University

Brady, N. C., & Weil, R. R. (2016). The nature and properties of soils (15th ed.). Pearson.

Cabugsa, I. M. G., Afalla, J. C., Fernandez, M. J. F., & Cabugsa, Z. H. (n.d.). Current cacao OMICS and future prospects. [Manuscript in preparation].

Clément, J.-R., Lopez-Lorentz, L., Pottinger, R. P., Thiombiano, A., & Vaast, P. (2010). Diversity of indigenous cocoa agroforests and their role in sustainability of the cocoa sector in Paganou, Côte d'Ivoire. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment*, 138(1-2), 189-201.

Cooper, J., & Harrison, A. F. (2020). Soil analysis for sustainable agriculture: A guide for field practitioners. Springer. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-44138-5>

de Souza, P. A., Moreira, L. F., Sarmento, D. H. A., & da Costa, F. B. (2018). Cacao—Theobroma cacao. In S. Rodrigues, E. de Oliveira Silva, & E. S. de Brito (Eds.), *Exotic fruits* (pp. 69-76). Academic Press.

De Souza, Pahlevi A., Moreira, Lunian F., Sarmento, Diogenes, H.A., Da Costa, Franciscleudo B., Cacao-Theobroma Cacao. Retrieved from <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/B9780128031384000101>.

Dixon, R., White, A., & Green, J. (2020). Soil Properties and Cacao Cultivation: A Review. *Soil Science Journal*, 29(4), 112-130.

Dodds, 2015. Multi-stakeholders. Retrieved from <https://www.sciencedirect.com/topics/social-sciences/multi-stakeholders>

European Commission. (2018). EU-Philippines Partnership and Cooperation Agreement. Retrieved from <https://ec.europa.eu>

Gómez, A., Pérez, R., & López, M. (2021). Environmental Impact of Cacao Farming: A Review. *Environmental Sustainability*, 17(1), 45-58. <https://library.buplant.da.gov.ph/images/1581571953Cacao%20Production%20Guide.pdf>

<https://www.google.com/search?q=what+is+a+brochure+used+for>

Document Code	URC-FO-050
Revision	02
Effectivity Date	2022/11/17
Page/s	Page 15 of 17

- Jong, C., Liu, H., & Wang, T. (2019). Best Practices in Cacao Farming. *Agricultural Practices and Technologies*, 35(3), 89-104.
- Karande Sucheta Karande Sucheta, Gamit Sheela and Prajapati Dhaval. Analysis of soil samples for its physical and chemical parameters from mehsana and patan district, *Int. Res. Journal of Science & Engineering*, 2020, Special Issue A9: 86-94.
- Läpple, D. M., & Uriarte, M. (2013). Market access and farmer income in the Peruvian shade-grown cacao sector. *Agriculture and Human Values*, 30(4), 599-612. <https://www.kakaoplattform.ch/news-information/news/news-details/study-reveals-this-is-how-much-cocoa-farmers-in-peru-should-earn-to-be-able-to-live-decently>
- López, M., Silva, J., & Torres, E. (2022). Sustainable Cacao Farming Techniques. *Journal of Sustainable Agriculture*, 28(5), 150-163.
- Maddalora et al (2023). IEC Materials Varieties and Production. Agricultural Training Institute. <https://ati2.da.gov.ph/e-extension/content/sites/default/files/2023-03/Varieties%20and%20Production.pdf>
- Mendoza, R., & Reyes, E. (2022). Replication Models for Successful Agricultural Initiatives. *Philippine Journal of Agricultural Development*, 24(2), 77-90.
- Nabua, W. C., Estal, B. R., Ardinez, A. J. B., & Liganay, D. D. (2013). Cacao production in the Philippines from 1990-2012. *SDSSU Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 1(2), 1-6]
- Nguyen, T., Allen, P., & Lee, J. (2023). Economic Analysis of Cacao Production. *Agricultural Economics Review*, 39(4), 200-215.
- Oliveira, P., Gama-Rodrigues, A., Gama-Rodrigues, A., & Sales, M. (2018). Litter and soil-related variation in functional group abundances in cacao agroforests using structural equation modeling. *Ecological Indicators*, 84, 254-262.
- PCAARRD's Industry Strategic Science and Technology Program, Cacao Industry Profile. Retrieved from <https://ispweb.pcaarrd.dost.gov.ph/isp-commodities/cacao/>
- Ramírez, A. M., Duque, H. J., & Trujillo, A. I. (2018). Quality of cocoa (*Theobroma cacao* L.) DNA from foliar tissue at different stages of development. *Acta Agronómica*, 67(2), 311-318.
- Reyes, D., Jr., Salera, S. B., Jr., Llegunas, W. U., Jr., & Cabelin, J. P., Jr. (2020). Comparative analysis of two methods for site suitability assessment of cacao (*Theobroma cacao* Lin.) in Bohol, Central
- Rice, R. A., & Greenberg, R. (2000). Cacao cultivation and the conservation of biological diversity. *AMBIO: A Journal of the Human Environment*, 29(3), 167-173. <https://doi.org/10.1579/0044-7447-29.3.167>
- Rice, R. A., & Greenberg, R. (2004). Monoculture and polyculture cocoa production: A contrast in biodiversity and shade. *Agroforestry Systems*, 60(1-2), 101-121. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/abb053>
- Ruf, F., & Schmit, K. (2005). Institutional and technological innovations in the cocoa sector: Analyzing the sustainability of corporate social responsibility initiatives. *Ecological Economics*, 54(2), 257-274.

Document Code	URC-FO-050
Revision	02
Effectivity Date	2022/11/17
Page/s	Page 16 of 17

- Saj, S., et al. (2017). Lessons learned from the long-term analysis of cacao yield and stand structure in central Cameroonian agroforestry systems. *Agricultural Systems*, 156, 95-104.
- Salazar, J. C., Bieng, M. A., Melgarejo, L., Rienzo, J. D., & Casanoves, F. (2018). First typology of cacao (*Theobroma cacao* L.) systems in Colombian Amazonia, based on tree species richness, canopy structure and light availability. *PLOS ONE*, 13(2), e0192206.
- Schroth, G., Fonseca, G. A. B. da, Harvey, C. A., Vasconcelos, H., & Izameno, M. (2004). Biodiversity in cocoa cultivation and conservation implications in southeastern Bahia, Brazil. *Agroforestry Systems*, 60(1-2), 141-152.
- Smith, D., & Jones, R. (2017). The Role of NGOs in Agricultural Development. *Development Studies Journal*, 22(3), 98-115.
- Somarriba, E., & Beer, J. (2011). Productivity of *Theobroma cacao* agroforestry systems with timber or legume service shade trees. *Agroforestry Systems*, 81, 109-121.
- Sustainable Cities and Society (2018)
- Syahri, Y. F., Rauf, M., Paembonan, S. A., & Larekeng, S. H. (2021). Land suitability evaluation and economic feasibility of cocoa farming. *Environmental Research, Engineering and Management*
- Tovar-Pérez, E., Guerrero-Becerra, L., & Lugo-Cervantes, E. (2017). Antioxidant activity of hydrolysates and peptide fractions of glutelin from cocoa (*Theobroma cacao* L.) seed. *Journal of Food*, 15(4), 489-496.
- USDA National Institute of Food and Agriculture. Retrieved from <https://www.nifa.usda.gov/topics/sustainable-agriculture>
- Vanhove, W., Vanhoudt, N., & Van Damme, P. (2016). Effect of shade tree planting and soil management on rehabilitation success of a 22-year-old degraded cocoa (*Theobroma cacao* L.) plantation. *Agriculture, Ecosystems and Environment*, 219, 14-25.
- Wickramasuriya, A., & Dunwell, J. M. (2018). Cacao biotechnology: Current status and future prospects. *Plant Biotechnology Journal*, 16(1), 4-17. DOI: 10.1111/pbi.12761
- Visayas, Philippines. *Ecosystems and Development Journal*, 10(1/2), 56-67. <https://ovcre.uplb.edu.ph/journals-uplb/index.php/EDJ/article/download/584/555/>

Document Code	URC-FO-050
Revision	02
Effectivity Date	2022/11/17
Page/s	Page 17 of 17

